

An AOP network of Neural Tube Defects

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Abstract

The shift towards animal-free approaches in toxicological risk assessment highlights the need for robust, mechanistic frameworks. The Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) is a framework that is increasingly used to provide a more mechanistic, human-relevant basis for the assessment of certain hazards. An AOP shows how a Molecular Initiation Event (MIE) is linked to an Adverse Outcome (AO) through a sequence of Key Events (KE). In this paper, we present an AOP for neural tube defects (NTD), a group of severe birth defects that result from failed neural tube closure (NTC). NTC occurs within a short time frame during the early stages of human development. It is a highly complex and sensitive process that relies on the precise regulation of genes and cell behavior. NTDs are one of the most common birth defects worldwide. To develop an AOP, existing literature was gathered on NTC and its pathologies, identifying the critical steps from MIE to AO. Overall, this putative AOP network provides a comprehensive overview of the underlying mechanisms of NTDs and offers a valuable tool to guide future research.

1 Introduction

The neural tube forms the embryonic foundation of the central nervous system (CNS), giving rise to the brain and spinal cord. In humans, neural tube closure (NTC) occurs during the third week of gestation [1]. During this process, the neural plate bends, the folds elevate, and the opposing edges fuse at the midline to form the tube [1, 2, 3]. Multiple signaling pathways and cell behaviors coordinate this sequence of events. Because of this complexity, disruptions from environmental, nutritional, or genetic factors are able to disturb NTC leading to neural tube defects (NTDs) [4, 5, 6]. NTDs include spina bifida, anencephaly, encephalocele, hydrocephalus, and craniorachischisis [6, 7]. NTDs represent one of the most common congenital malformations, affecting an estimated 214,000 to 322,000 pregnancies worldwide each year [8, 9].

Research has not yet fully explained how exposures such as inadequate folate intake or toxicant exposure leads to NTDs. Rodent-based guideline studies for developmental toxicity, including OECD (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development) test guideline (TG) 414 and guideline 870.3700 from the Office of Prevention, Pesticides Toxic Substances (OPPTS; US Environmental Protection Agency), remain the primary tools [10]. Although species differences limit extrapolation to humans, the basic mechanisms of NTC are highly conserved across mammals [11]. This conservation provides mechanistic insights from animal studies, which remain essential given ethical restrictions on human research [12]. To predict how molecular perturbations lead to adverse outcomes, we need frameworks that connect early biological events to clinical endpoints and that can support the development of animal-free testing strategies.

The Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) provides such a framework. An AOP describes how a molecular initiating event (MIE), triggered by an external or internal stressor, leads through a sequence of key events (KEs) to an adverse outcome (AO) [13, 14]. Key event relationships (KERs) define the causal links between levels of biological organization, from molecular interactions to tissue and organ effects. The AOP approach has gained prominence as a mechanistic tool in toxicology and risk assessment [15].

There are currently four AOPs available in the AOP-wiki (<https://aopwiki.org/>) that describe neural tube defects as the AO (IDs 572, 449, 434, and 275). These AOPs start at the MIEs: BMP4 suppression, ceramide synthase disruption, CYP26 inhibition, and histone deacetylase inhibition, and each captures only a single causal chain [16]. These linear representations provide valuable insights into isolated mechanisms but do not reflect the interconnected and multi-factorial nature of neural tube closure. Because this developmental process depends on the coordinated activity of multiple signaling pathways, cellular behaviors, and tissue morphogenesis, a network-based perspective is required. In this study, we construct a putative qualitative AOP network that integrates molecular, cellular, and tissue-level mechanisms of neural tube closure. This framework establishes a foundation for the development of quantitative AOPs and dynamic systems modeling, and provides a more comprehensive basis for predictive toxicology and regulatory application.

2 Methods

We followed a structured workflow to construct a qualitative AOP for neural tube defects (NTDs). First, we conducted a comprehensive literature search and screening to identify relevant mechanistic studies. Next, from relevant literature we extracted information on molecular players, cellular behaviors, signaling pathways, and tissue-level processes related to neural tube closure (NTC). Subsequently, we used this evidence to construct an AOP diagram in which key events (KEs) and key event relationships (KERs) were visualized and scored for confidence and strength. This approach ensured a systematic and transparent integration of available knowledge.

2.1 Literature search

We conducted a structured, evidence-based literature search to establish a qualitative AOP for NTDs. All literature was retrieved from the U.S. National Library of Medicine’s PubMed database, with the last search performed in April 2025. The search included a comprehensive set of keywords related to NTC anatomical structures (e.g., notochord, neural groove), metabolic pathways (e.g., folic acid cycle, one-carbon metabolism), cel-

lular behaviors (e.g., neural crest cell migration, actin turnover), and signaling pathways (e.g., Shh, Wnt, RHOA).

The following query terms were used: Neural tube defects, NTD, Neural tube formation, Neural tube closure, NTC, Neural tube development, Neural tube fusion, Surface ectoderm, Paraxial mesoderm, Notochord, Neural crest, Median hinge point, Dorsolateral hinge points, Neuroectoderm, Neuro ectoderm, Neural groove, Cytoskeletal reorganization, Neural crest cell migration, Neural crest cell delamination, Epidermis formation, Actin turnover, Hinge point, Folic acid cycle, Methylation, One-carbon metabolism, DNA synthesis, Folate uptake, Histone deacetylase, HDAC, Ceramide synthase, Sphingolipid metabolism, Lipid rafts, ROS, SHH, BMP, FGF, WNT, TGF- β , CDH, RDH, FST, ZIC, RHOA.

To maintain focus, keywords were divided into two groups. The first group (Neural tube defects, NTD, Neural tube formation, Neural tube closure, NTC, Neural tube development, Neural tube fusion) was constrained to title and abstract searches. The remaining keywords were applied without restriction. No limits were placed on publication year; all available articles were considered.

2.2 Screening

We screened articles using Sysrev¹, a web-based platform for collaborative screening and data extraction. In our Sysrev project (cloned from an earlier template), the built-in prediction feature generated an inclusion-likelihood score for each record, which allowed articles to be prioritized during screening[17].

Prior to screening, we defined a set of labels: five Boolean labels (Include, Review, Toxicity, Genetic focus, Nutrient deficiency) and three categorical labels (Species: Human, Rat, Mouse, Zebrafish, Xenopus, Chick, Rabbit, Guinea Pig, Monkey, Other; Experimental design: Patients/human tissue, *In vivo*, *In vitro*, *In silico*, None; Biological level: Molecular, Tissue, NA).

Initially, 580 of 1328 articles were manually screened based on title and abstract. This subset was also used to train and optimize the Sysrev machine learning algorithm for inclusion prediction. Screening then continued within Sysrev up to 693 articles, focusing on high-probability papers (inclusion probability > 0.925).

Articles labeled as “include: yes” were exported and categorized in Excel into four groups: toxicological studies, reviews, nutrient deficiency studies, and other relevant

¹<https://www.sysrev.com/>

studies. We then assessed open access availability using the Unpaywall web tool (version 2, accessed May 2025)². Non-open access articles (147 of 319) were excluded from further screening. Open access articles were manually evaluated, supported by generative AI tools (Google AI Studio, Gemini Pro 2.5, Jan 2025). Screening focused on results- and discussion sections to extract mechanistic details. Exact numbers are displayed in the supplementary material.

From each article, we extracted: (i) genes or molecular players, (ii) interaction details, (iii) cellular/tissue compartments, (iv) key events, (v) signaling pathways, (vi) downstream effects, (vii) developmental timing, and (viii) AOP relevance. In total, 63 articles were used for AOP development. Most were retrieved from PubMed, supplemented by reviews and Ontox project publications.

2.3 AOP construction and consolidation

We visualized and constructed the AOP using Draw.io (v28.0.6)³. Color coding distinguished biological levels: green for molecular initiating events, yellow for cellular signaling key events, light orange for cellular shaping/patterning events, dark orange for tissue morphogenesis events, and red for the adverse outcome (AO) at organ level.

Each key event relationship (KER) was assessed for strength, defined as the degree of supporting evidence. Each key event (KE) was assessed for confidence. In the diagram, KER strength was visualized by arrow thickness, and KE certainty by outline thickness (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: **Legend for AOP components.** Colors indicate biological levels: green for molecular initiating events, yellow for cellular signaling, light orange for cellular shaping/patterning, dark orange for tissue morphogenesis, and red for the adverse outcome. Arrow thickness reflects KER strength, and outline thickness indicates KE certainty.

2.4 Criteria for KE certainty and KER strength

We applied two structured criteria to evaluate robustness of the AOP: (i) certainty of each KE and (ii) strength of each KER. Each criterion comprises five scoring categories.

Key event certainty:

- **Established (5):** KE is reproducible and reported consistently in many studies, with strong evidence from human data (clinical, epidemiological, or patient cohorts).

²<https://unpaywall.org/>

³<https://app.diagrams.net/>

- **Strong (4):** KE is consistently observed in independent studies across laboratories with diverse designs, mainly in mammalian in vivo systems or advanced human in vitro models (e.g., organoids, 3D cultures).
- **Modest (3):** KE is reported in multiple studies with some discrepancies or consistent but limited evidence, predominantly from mammalian in vivo models.
- **Observed (2):** KE is observed in non-mammalian in vivo models (e.g., zebrafish, Xenopus). Consistency across studies supports validity despite evolutionary distance.
- **Weak (1):** KE is reported in a limited number of studies, often single-lab findings, or only in simple in vitro systems.
- **Unconfirmed (0):** Evidence exists only from in silico models without biological validation, or data are contradictory.

Key event relationship strength:

- **Established (5)**: Supported by direct human evidence, e.g., gene mutations in NTD patients.
- **Strong (4)**: Demonstrated consistently in independent studies using targeted experimental manipulation (e.g., CRISPR editing, knock-outs/knockdowns).
- **Modest (3)**: Shown consistently across studies with functional validation, mainly pharmacological interventions. Less direct than loss-of-function evidence.
- **Observed (2)**: Supported by preliminary experimental evidence (e.g., pharmacological modulation, overexpression) but lacks targeted manipulation.
- **Weak (1)**: Limited evidence from a few studies, often from the same laboratory. Considered insufficient to establish a causal link.
- **Unconfirmed (0)**: No evidence supporting the KER, or strong contradictory data.

3 Results

We assembled a qualitative AOP for neural tube defects (NTDs) that links candidate molecular initiating events (MIEs) to cellular and tissue-level key events (KEs) that converge on failed neural tube closure (Figure 2). We summarized KE certainty and KER strength in the visualization, using the criteria described in Section 2.4 and the legend in Figure 1.

Figure 2: Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) for neural tube defects. Color-coding indicates biological levels, and visual elements represent KE certainty and KER strength.

The AOP network is presented in four sections, each highlighting a specific pathway: (3.1) disruption of PCP/Wnt signaling and failure of apical constriction and convergent extension, (3.2) aberrant dorsoventral and anteroposterior morphogen gradients leading to defective neural tube patterning, (3.3) altered Grainyhead-like (Grhl) activity impairing epithelial adhesion, and (3.4) dysregulated RhoGTPase and EphA/ephrinA signaling causing failed neural fold fusion. We did not display section-specific MIEs as separate nodes in the network, because the number of plausible MIEs would crowd the figure;

instead, we describe putative MIEs for each sub-network in the accompanying text.

3.1 Disruption of PCP/Wnt signaling impairs apical constriction and convergent extension

Successful neural tube closure (NTC) requires coordinated morphogenetic processes. The Wnt/planar cell polarity (PCP) pathway is central to this process, as it controls cell orientation and movement within the neural plate [18]. PCP signaling regulates two key cellular movements: convergent extension (CE) and apical constriction (AC) [19]. Disruptions can dysregulate downstream effectors such as RhoA/ROCK, impairing actomyosin function and thereby interfering with CE and AC. These failures result in defective elongation and narrowing of the neural plate, improper hinge point bending, and increased neuroepithelial (NE) tension (Figure 3) [20].

CE drives elongation and narrowing of the neural plate by medio-lateral cell intercalation and convergence toward the midline, producing anteroposterior elongation of axial

Figure 3: AOP sub-network highlighting the role of Wnt/PCP signaling in convergent extension and apical constriction during neural tube closure. Disruptions in PCP signaling impair actomyosin dynamics, leading to NTDs.

tissues [20, 21]. Core PCP proteins, including Frizzled (Fzd), Dishevelled (Dvl), Celsr, Vangl, Prickle, and Ankrd6, are required for this process [19, 20]. Mislocalization or reduction of these proteins impairs CE, leading to failure of neural plate narrowing and elongation.

Evidence from model organisms supports this link. In *Xenopus*, impaired CE caused excessive widening of the neural plate and NTDs [22]. Mouse studies show that mutations in *Vangl2*, *Celsr1*, *Dvl1/2*, *Fzd3*, and *Fzd6* lead to craniorachischisis [2, 8, 23, 24]. In humans, putative mutations in PCP genes such as *Vangl1*, *Vangl2*, *Celsr1*, *Dvl2*, *Fzd6*, and *Prickle1* have been identified in NTD patients [2, 19, 23, 25]. CE depends on actomyosin-mediated cytoskeletal remodeling. In chick neuroepithelium, *Celsr1* polarizes AP-junctions and activates *Dvl* and *Daam1*, leading to RhoA/myosin-mediated contraction [2]. PCP dysfunction therefore affects CE indirectly by interfering with actomyosin dynamics through RhoA/ROCK [20, 22, 26, 27].

RhoA/ROCK activity also regulates AC, which is required for bending of the neural plate at hinge points, including dorsolateral hinge points (DLHPs) and the median hinge point (MHP) [2, 28, 29]. AC reshapes neuroepithelial cells by actomyosin contraction at

the apical surface, narrowing their apical diameter [20, 30]. While AC is crucial in cranial regions [27], its role in spinal closure is less consistent, as closure can occur even when actin polymerization is inhibited [27, 31].

Excessive actomyosin can also impair closure. Overaccumulation of actomyosin increases NE stiffness and prevents fold elevation, despite hinge point formation [20, 27, 32]. In *Vangl2* mutant mice, reduced apical F-actin polarization decreased biomechanical resilience at the zippering point [25, 33]. *Zic2* mutant mice similarly showed aberrant actomyosin accumulation and increased stiffness, both linked to caudal spina bifida [34].

Disruption of Wnt/PCP signaling interferes with RhoA/ROCK-mediated actomyosin dynamics [28, 29]. These perturbations impair convergent extension and apical constriction, leading to defective neural plate shaping and increased risk of spina bifida. Together, these findings highlight how disrupted PCP signaling alters the mechanical forces that shape the neural plate. In the next section, we focus on how abnormal signaling gradients along the dorsoventral and anteroposterior axes disturb neural tube patterning.

Possible molecular initiating events. This AOP section initiate when a perturbation reduces non-canonical Wnt5a/Wnt11 input or disrupts assembly and cortical localization of the core PCP complex. Candidate MIEs therefore include impaired Frizzled function, altered Dishevelled (Dvl) recruitment or stability, and mislocalization or loss-of-function of *Vangl*, *Celsr*, or *Prickle*. These initiating perturbations can weaken Daam1-dependent RhoA activation and ROCK-mediated myosin regulation, which reduces junctional actomyosin polarization that drives convergent extension and apical constriction. Several exposures can plausibly enter this sub-network by disrupting cytoskeletal organization and actomyosin contractility, including 2,4-D and caffeine. Dithiocarbamates such as thiram can also act as indirect initiators by perturbing axial tissue integrity and biomechanics, which can secondarily challenge PCP-dependent neural plate shaping. Also α -solanine and its metabolite solanidine represent candidate initiators because they have been described to disrupt Wnt/PCP signaling and inhibit JNK activity, which can reduce PCP output and downstream cytoskeletal polarization [35].

3.2 Aberrant morphogen gradients disrupt neural tube patterning

Precise dorsoventral (D-V) and anteroposterior (A-P) signaling gradients are essential for neural tube patterning. Secreted morphogens such as BMP, Shh, FGF, Wnt/ β -catenin, and RA regulate these gradients and define cellular identity according to concentration [36].

Figure 4: AOP sub-network summarizing the role of dorsoventral (D-V) and antero-posterior (A-P) morphogen gradients in neural tube patterning. Dysregulation of these gradients impairs hinge point formation and neural crest specification, leading to NTDs.

D-V patterning relies on gradients of BMP, secreted dorsally by the non-neural ectoderm, and Shh, secreted ventrally by the notochord [2, 37]. Disruption of BMP signaling impairs cell fate specification and hinge point formation (Figure 4). For instance, excess BMP activity enhances NE proliferation, delays closure, and prematurely induces neural crest cell (NCC) specification in *Fgf3* mutants [38, 39, 40]. Conversely, BMP inhibition together with high levels of TGF β in chick midbrain prevented MHP formation, causing failed elevation and fusion [41]. Overactivation of BMP in *Zic2* mutants blocked DLHP formation, while BMP inhibition restored it, confirming its causal role [34, 42].

BMP antagonists such as Chordin and Noggin are critical for gradient balance [2]. Noggin deficiency elevates BMP activity and promotes ectopic Shh expression, leading to exencephaly [43]. In *Zic2* mutants, loss of both Noggin and Neuralin caused complete DLHP failure [42].

Shh signaling is mediated through Gli transcription factors regulated by the primary cilium [44, 45]. Overactivation of Shh, often due to loss of negative regulators such as Rab23, Tulp3, or *Sufu*, disrupts patterning [20]. In *Ehd1* mutants, ciliary defects suppressed Gli3 repressor activity, leading to Shh overactivation and NTDs [46]. Similar effects caused by mutations in ciliary genes such as *TOLOGRAM1* have been linked to spina bifida in humans [47].

Patterning along the A-P axis depends on balanced FGF, Wnt/ β -catenin, and RA signaling [36, 48, 49, 50, 51]. FGF maintains neuromesodermal progenitors and regulates motility and metabolism during caudal elongation [52]. Wnt/ β -catenin activity regulates transcription factors *Cdx2* and *Pax3*. Loss of β -catenin reduces *fgf8* expression and causes truncations and spina bifida [53]. Similarly, *Lrp6* mutations downregulate *Pax3* and result in spina bifida [54]. RA opposes FGF and Wnt to define positional identity. It regulates Hox gene expression through retinoic acid response elements (RAREs), defining rhombomere segmentation in the hindbrain [55, 56, 57]. RA deficiency or altered metabolism disrupts Hox expression and causes regional defects [58, 59, 60].

Aberrant BMP, Shh, FGF, Wnt/ β -catenin, or RA signaling disturbs dorsoventral and anteroposterior gradients. Such disruptions impair hinge point formation and neural crest specification, causing defective neural tube patterning and closure failure. While morphogen gradients establish the overall body plan and hinge point positioning, successful closure also requires intact epithelial integrity. We therefore examined the role of Grainyhead-like (*Grhl*) transcription factors in maintaining adhesion during neural fold fusion.

Possible molecular initiating events. This AOP section can initiate when a perturbation alters morphogen production, transport, reception, or degradation and thereby distorts effective BMP, Shh, FGF, Wnt/ β -catenin, or RA gradients. Candidate MIEs include increased BMP receptor activation or reduced BMP antagonism, altered Shh pathway activation through Smoothened or cilium-dependent Gli processing, and altered RA synthesis or catabolism that shifts RA availability. This sub-network can also initiate through altered Wnt/ β -catenin or FGFR signaling that destabilizes caudal progenitor programs and anteroposterior identity. Small molecules with defined pathway targets support these entry points, including cyclopamine as a Smoothened inhibitor and all-trans retinoic acid as a direct retinoid receptor agonist. Environmental exposures have also

been reported to perturb BMP–Shh balance or retinoid homeostasis, including imidacloprid, Ochratoxin A, and azole fungicides such as tebuconazole, which can shift gradient interpretation during neurulation.

3.3 Altered Grhl activity impairs epithelial adhesion

The Grainyhead-like (Grhl) transcription factors, particularly Grhl2 and Grhl3, are essential for maintaining epithelial integrity during NTC [2]. Knockouts in mice cause spina bifida and exencephaly, demonstrating their role in epithelial adhesion [20, 61] (Figure 5).

Figure 5: AOP sub-network describing the role of Grainyhead-like (Grhl) transcription factors in epithelial adhesion and biomechanics. Disrupted Grhl activity impairs adhesion and increases stiffness, resulting in failed neural fold fusion.

Grhl regulates expression of adhesion molecules such as E-cadherin, N-cadherin, claudin-4, and Rab25 [2]. It also suppresses epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition (EMT), maintaining epithelial stability [62, 63]. Loss of Grhl2 reduces NNE integrity and enhances EMT, contributing to failed fusion [62]. Grhl2 mutants show decreased E-cadherin and failed fold fusion [64], while Grhl overexpression causes excessive adhesion, tissue stiffness, and disrupted junction remodeling [31]. Grhl3 knockouts also prevent fusion and cause spinal NTDs [65].

Although adhesion is central, disruption of single adhesion proteins such as N-cadherin is insufficient to cause NTDs [66], whereas early lethality of E-cadherin knockouts complicates assessment [61, 67]. Grhl likely contributes through multiple targets and intersects with other signaling pathways, including Wnt/ β , PCP, and BMP antagonists [68, 69, 70].

Reduced or excessive Grhl activity alters epithelial adhesion and biomechanics in the non-neural ectoderm. These changes compromise neural fold fusion, demonstrating that

Grhl regulates NTC through multiple interconnected downstream targets[2, 70]. Grhl factors ensure the biomechanical properties of the non-neural ectoderm, but final closure depends on cellular protrusions and adhesion signals at the fusion site. The next section describes how RhoGTPases and EphA/ephrinA signaling coordinate this last stage of neural tube closure.

Possible molecular initiating events. This AOP section can initiate when a perturbation reduces or increases Grhl2/Grhl3 transcriptional activity in the non-neural

ectoderm. Candidate MIEs include reduced *Grhl* expression, impaired DNA binding or co-factor recruitment, or sustained *Grhl* overactivity that locks epithelial junction programs. These initiating perturbations alter expression of adhesion and polarity targets and they can shift the balance between epithelial maintenance and EMT-like programs. Several exposures can plausibly enter this sub-network by perturbing epithelial junction homeostasis and transcriptional programs that intersect with adhesion control, including azole fungicides such as *tebuconazole*. Cytoskeletal disruptors such as 2,4-D and caffeine can further contribute by limiting junction remodeling and epithelial cohesion during neural fold apposition. Other possible chemical disrupters are *methotrexate hydrate* and *nicotine* represent candidate initiators because they can disrupt folate-dependent proliferation and epithelial junction homeostasis, respectively, which can reduce epithelial integrity at the fusion interface.

3.4 Dysregulated RhoGTPase and EphA/ephrinA signaling prevents neural fold fusion

Neural fold fusion is the final step in NTC, requiring initial contact between opposing folds and coordinated reorganization of the neuroepithelium (NE) and non-neural ectoderm (NNE) [2]. Dynamic filopodia and lamellipodia mediate this contact, with their cellular origin depending on the region along the anterior–posterior axis [26] (Figure 6).

Figure 6: AOP sub-network highlighting the role of Rho GTPases and EphA/ephrinA signaling in neural fold fusion. Dysregulation of these mechanisms prevents initial contact or adhesion of the neural folds, resulting in failed neural tube closure.

Small Rho GTPases such as *Rac1* and *Cdc42* regulate protrusion formation and thus the reorganization of the actin cytoskeleton required to drive filopodia and lamellipodia [2, 61, 71]. *Rac1* knockout mice lack ruffles and fail to initiate midline contact, preventing fusion [26]. The role of *Cdc42* is less clear: early defects occur, but mutants suggest filopodia may not be strictly required [32].

Adhesion between folds also depends on Eph-ephrin signaling. Eph receptors and ephrin ligands mediate cell–cell recognition at the midline. Loss of ephrin-A5 or *EphA7* causes cranial NTDs, where folding occurs but fusion fails [61]. In spinal closure, disruption of *EphA/ephrinA* delays closure [8, 72]. These data show that both RhoGTPase

dysfunction and Eph-ephrin disruption impair neural fold fusion and thus contribute to NTDs (Figure 6).

Possible molecular initiating events. This AOP section can initiate when a perturbation alters small Rho GTPase activation states or disrupts EphA–ephrinA engagement at the fusion interface. Candidate MIEs include reduced Rac1 or Cdc42 activation, impaired upstream GEF-mediated GTP loading, and reduced actin-nucleation capacity that limits protrusion dynamics. Candidate MIEs also include reduced EphA receptor signaling or ephrin-A ligand function that weakens midline recognition and adhesion. Several exposures have been reported to disrupt actin or microtubule organization and can therefore plausibly reduce protrusion formation and contact stabilization, including 2,4-D and thiram. Exposures that perturb neural crest-associated migration and adhesion programs, including imidacloprid, glyphosate and tebuconazole can also plausibly impair coordinated tissue rearrangement at the fusion site.

4 Conclusion & Discussion

Neural tube defects (NTDs) remain a major health concern worldwide. Understanding how molecular-level disruptions contribute to their development is therefore essential. In this study, we constructed an AOP network that integrates molecular, cellular, and tissue-level events relevant to the etiology of NTDs. This network highlights essential mechanisms, such as the role of non-canonical Wnt/PCP signaling in apical constriction and convergent extension, and the contribution of FGF, RA, BMP/TGF β , Shh, and Wnt/ β signaling in neural tube patterning. It further emphasizes the role of *Grhl* in epithelial integrity, and the importance of EphA/ephrinA and RhoGTPases in neural fold fusion. Collectively, this network establishes a foundation for improving human-relevant risk assessment strategies.

This work advances the understanding of chemical-induced NTDs by moving beyond the linear AOPs currently listed in the AOP-Wiki (IDs 572, 449, 434, and 275) [16]. While these AOPs provide insight into specific mechanisms, they typically describe single MIEs leading to a linear series of key events. For instance, AOP 275 describes how HDAC inhibition increases histone acetylation, alters gene expression, and disrupts differentiation, ultimately producing NTDs. In contrast, the present AOP network captures the complexity of interacting mechanisms. Several key events, such as actomyosin disruption or morphogen gradient dysfunction, are shared across developmental processes. Their reusability supports the construction of future AOPs, increasing consistency and efficiency [13]. Beyond the scientific community, this network can inform regulatory and policy decisions on chemical safety, and it can help industry optimize product safety evaluation while limiting animal testing [73].

The AOP concept is central to the development of New Approach Methodologies (NAMs). Rather than relying solely on traditional animal tests, NAMs can make use of AOPs to provide mechanistic insight into how chemicals induce harm [14, 74]. Computational tools, such as quantitative structure–activity relationship (QSAR) models, allow prediction of a chemical’s ability to trigger an MIE. QSAR models link molecular descriptors with biological activity by training on large datasets of well-characterized compounds. Once trained, these models can predict whether a novel substance is likely to trigger a given MIE [74].

This qualitative AOP also provides a basis for quantitative AOPs (qAOPs). Quantifi-

cation requires mathematical definition of KERs, supported by robust dose–response and concentration–effect data. Depending on available data and research goals, models can range from simple regression approaches to dynamic systems models such as Boolean networks or agent-based models [75, 76]. This AOP network can guide such modeling efforts by providing a mechanistic template of relevant biological interactions in the context of NTDs. Combining qAOPs with toxicokinetic (TK) models further enables cross-species extrapolation and human dose estimation. In this network, internal concentrations linked to adverse effects can be translated into external exposure doses relevant for human safety [75].

This AOP should be regarded as a first attempt at constructing a qualitative AOP network for human neural tube defects. The KEs and KERs described here comprise biologically plausible connections that require further investigation to be consolidated. For the purpose of consolidation of the network towards OECD review, also aspects like empirical evidence (dose and time concordance) and essentiality of the KEs and KERs needs to be determined [10]. In this light, a number of limitations must be noted. First, the network may reflect publication bias. Well-studied pathways, such as PCP signaling, are overrepresented compared with less accessible or less frequently studied mechanisms. This prominence does not necessarily indicate greater biological importance but rather differences in experimental tractability. For example, defects in MHP and DLHP formation are easily observable, whereas more subtle changes such as excessive neuroepithelial tension are more difficult to detect and may therefore be underreported. Another aspect of publication bias further contributes to this imbalance, as studies with statistically significant findings are more likely to be published than those with negative results [77]. The strong representation of PCP signaling may partly reflect this trend.

Second, evidence selection bias may also be present. Given the large body of literature on NTC, we applied a keyword-based approach to ensure focus and feasibility. While effective, this approach may have emphasized some mechanisms over others, for example under representing neural crest-related processes. Restricting certain keywords to titles and abstracts may also have excluded relevant studies addressing NTC in the broader context of embryogenesis.

Third, the current AOP treats neural tube closure as a single, pooled process and does not assign molecular and cellular mechanisms to specific closure sites along the anterior–posterior axis. Because NTC mechanisms vary regionally, including differences in hinge point architecture and closure requirements between cranial and spinal regions, this abstraction reduces defect-type specificity [20, 78]. Future refinements should therefore incorporate regional annotations or site-specific sub-AOPs to improve predictive resolution.

Finally, the majority of supporting evidence is derived from animal studies, with limited input from human data and *in vitro* systems. Although core mechanisms of NTC are highly conserved among mammals [11], species differences remain a limitation for direct extrapolation to humans. *In vitro* models can provide additional insight, but it should be noted that these lack the complexity of three-dimensional embryonic morphogenesis [79].

Despite these limitations, this study presents a putative AOP network that reflects the multifactorial etiology of NTDs. By moving beyond linear frameworks, it captures the interconnected biology of neural tube closure and provides a platform for mechanistic toxicology. This network can support the advancement of NAMs, and thus aid in promoting replacement, reduction, and refinement (3Rs) in toxicology. Overall, the framework represents a step toward more predictive and human-relevant risk assessment.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Job H Berkhout: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Alessia van der Sluis:** Methodology, Investigation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Aldert H Piersma** Funding acquisition, review. **Harm J Heusinkveld** Funding acquisition, project administration, supervision and review.

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study. The AOP will be published integrally in the AOP-Wiki.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary Figure: Prisma chart of literature study